

D10.3. OEI - Requirement No. 3

C. Sardeli, Independent Ethics Advisor

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-centre clinical trial.

Deliverable D10.2 Description

According to the opinions of the ethics experts that evaluated the submitted proposal prior to its funding, the proposal raised several ethics issues. Among others, that the clinical trial C1 requires a continuous DVT monitoring of high-risk patients (postoperative and mostly bedridden), using the ThrombUS+ wearable device, from 12 hours after surgery and for 3 days. This raised questions about the vulnerability of the participants and their autonomy, especially because the applicants missed to indicate participation of vulnerable individuals in Part A Ethics Issues Table. Furthermore, partner PBY was presented as “social sciences expert involved in health technology deployments” to advise on the clinical studies/trials protocols (Section 2 - Preparedness status - in 3 clinical studies and 2 clinical trials descriptions); however, this is a research and consulting firm specialising in data and behavioural science to advise organisations on decision-making processes. Its expertise is not particularly relevant to address issues of autonomy and vulnerability in patients participating in clinical trials.

Due to the abovementioned, it was indicated that the project must appoint an Ethics Advisor with expertise in human-centred technology (AI-powered technology in particular), to help prioritise the well-being of the participants in the clinical trials and studies, to help the project adopt an ethics-by-design approach (rather than a conformity-by-design technical approach) for the development of ThrombUS – ThrombUS+. A report by the ethics advisor must be submitted to cover these issues every year starting at M12.

D10.3 is the second yearly report compiled by the Independent Ethics Advisor appointed by the Consortium.

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Sardeli C., ThrombUS+ Ethics Appraisal Report #2, Deliverable D10.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 18 December 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17963777>, Publishable Summary.

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
DVT	Deep vein thrombosis
EC	European Commission
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Specialists
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
hE	Human Embryos
hESC	Human Embryonic Stem Cells
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
OEI	Other Ethics Issues
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identification
PGNA	University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli, Associated Partner newly admitted to the Consortium

Report by the Independent Ethics Advisor

Funding Programme	Horizon Europe
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Acronym	ThrombUS+
Project Title	Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis
Project start date-end date	1 January 2024 – 30 June 2027
Period covered	M13 – M24 Jan 2025 to Dec 2025

1. Name and Contact Details

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Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=6506769092>

2. Overview of ethics issues raised by the project activities

2.1. Project activities timing and progress

Overall, project activities are progressing according to the GA and the approved workplan.

There has been a delay in the recruitment in Study A, however this has been documented in the Interim Report #1 and mitigated. Study A has received all necessary ethics approvals and is now progressing steadily in five different sites (with the replacement of TAU by PGNA).

The **main ethics issues** raised during this second project year are related to the **Clinical Studies B**.

As already documented in the Interim Report #1, Clinical Study B2 was split into 3 different studies to allow for coherence in implementation. As a result, Studies B are as follows:

Clinical Study B1: A multi-centre cohort study for ultrasound image set collection via ThrombUS+ prototype ultrasound components to create a training data set for research purposes (image processing and analysis, AI training).

Clinical Study B2: A single-centre observational cohort study to collect lower limb activity measurements from healthy volunteers during physiotherapy exercises using commercial inertial measurement units

(IMUs) and camera sensors to create a training data set for research purposes (signal processing and analysis, AI training).

Clinical Study B3: A single-centre observational cohort study to collect lower limb activity measurements from healthy volunteers during physiotherapy exercises using the inertial measurement unit (IMU) system developed in ThrombUS+ and commercial fixed position cameras with the aim to test and optimize IMU performance and fusion algorithms for human motion tracking.

Clinical Study B4: Pilot phase clinical investigation to collect electrical impedance plethysmography data set from healthy volunteers and DVT patients using the ThrombUS+ prototype device developed during the project and a commercially available equivalent device as a reference.

Studies B are planned as studies to collect signals and data to be used for training machine learning models and/or developing signal processing and analysis algorithms. The studies are planned **to use experimental data collection components developed in the project** and thus not yet certified for commercial use. An exception is Study B2, which uses solely commercial, certified activity sensors.

Ethics related procedures have been respected, and the current status of attaining the necessary ethics approvals is as follows: all ongoing studies have been submitted for ethics assessment to relevant authorities and said authorisation has been attained for all participating sites. Planned pending studies have either been submitted for ethics assessment to relevant authorities or are in the process of submission for ethics assessment to relevant authorities prior to their initiation.

2.2. Deviations from the ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report

No deviations from the ethics issues included in the Ethics Summary Report have been identified. Project activities in months M12-M24 have not raised any additional specific ethical concerns.

The Consortium has been advised of their obligations to reapply for ethics approvals every time they complete the planning of a new clinical trial. They have also asked for and received advice on how to best recruit study participants in a manner that respects their rights and situation, as indicated during the Ethics Assessment process of the project prior to its obtaining funding.

The Consortium has also been advised that adopting an ethics-by-design approach means that they should make a conscious effort to ensure that the final product does not record more information than absolutely necessary for the aims of the project and that all information pertaining to possible threats to personal rights and freedom of participants and future users (should the product be made commercially available) is readily available to them.

2.3. Ethics issues considered no longer applicable

Not applicable.

3. Ethics Analysis

3.1. Overview of the management of project's activities in relation to ethics

The project management, on behalf of the Consortium, complied to the ethics requirements included in the GA by appointing an Independent Ethics Advisor, by providing them full access to the files of the project, by meeting regularly with the Independent Ethics Advisor and by actively seeking and receiving advice on how to best conduct their work. Collaboration involved all project aspects, focusing on the Clinical Studies planned to be dealt with during second year of the project work plan. This way the project management ensured that project activities run on time for this reporting period and are in accordance with the ethics requirements of the GA.

3.2. Activities of the Ethics Advisor

The Independent Ethics Advisor accessed and reviewed all project documents and select relevant recordings of project meetings located in the project's private shared workspace (Teams/SharePoint), participated in regular meetings with the management and select Consortium members, offered advice on the ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report but also on possible ways for the Consortium to adopt an ethics-by-design approach.

The particular ethics issue with Studies B (specifically, Studies B1, B3, and B4) relates to the fact that these studies plan to use **experimental, non-CE-marked components** developed within the ThrombUS+ project. These components are used exclusively for **research data collection purposes** and are not intended for diagnostic or therapeutic use.

The Ethics Advisor engaged in and contributed to the consortium discussions to address the above issue following regulations and best practices.

Elaboration and deliberations resulted in the following course of action: For each ThrombUS+ developed component to be used in a clinical study:

- A comprehensive risk assessment was carried out, with the involvement of technical partners, VDE and reviewed by the Ethics Advisor
- All potential risks associated with the use of the experimental components were systematically identified and analysed
- Appropriate risk mitigation measures were defined and implemented
- Residual risks were assessed and documented
- Technical safety testing was conducted by respective partners.

All risk analysis activities, safety assessments, mitigation measures, and conclusions are fully documented in the study protocol. The overall residual risk is considered "acceptable".

Ethics approval for Studies B1, B3 and B4 is requested by the respective Ethics Committees of the participating partners under Article 82 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (Medical Devices Regulation), as these studies constitute scientific research. These studies:

- do not aim to demonstrate clinical performance or conformity of a medical device
- do not involve diagnostic or therapeutic use of the prototype system
- do not influence clinical decision-making or patient management.

The prototype components are used solely for data acquisition in a research context.

Given the scientific research nature of the studies under Article 82 MDR and the documented minimal risk profile demonstrated through the risk analysis and safety assessments, no additional study-specific insurance is foreseen at this stage. All relevant documentation has nevertheless been provided to the competent Ethics Committees to allow them to assess independently whether additional insurance coverage is required, in accordance with national and institutional requirements.

3.3. Documents available to the Ethics Advisor

The Consortium has granted full access to the project's private shared workspace (Teams/SharePoint) and made sure that all project materials are readily available for inspection by the independent Ethics Advisor.

3.4. Overview of evidence of ethics compliance

Below is a list of ethics approvals pertaining to the studies considered in the 2nd year of the project.

3.4.1. Clinical Study B1

1.	Beneficiary	10 – LSMU
	Committee	Kaunas Regional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee, Kaunas, Lithuania
	Contact	A. Mickevičiaus g. 9, LT 44307 Kaunas, Lithuania
	Submission date	27.11.2025
	Approval	pending
2.	Beneficiary	11 – GNP
	Committee	Ethics Committee, Research Council, General Hospital Papagergiou,
	Contact	Papanikolaou Avenue, TK57010, Thessaloniki, Greece
	Submission date	First submission 05/11/2025 Pesubmission 02/03/2025, protocol no. 32327/3-12-2025
	Approval	Expected approval mid January
3.	Beneficiary	12 – CSS-IRCCS
	Committee	Comitato Etico Fondazione Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza
	Contact	Viale Cappuccini, San Giovanni Rotondo, Foggia zipcode: 71043, Italy
	Submission overview	Clinical Study A
	Submission date	pending
	Approval	pending
4.	Beneficiary	13 – HSV
	Committee	ANSM or CPP or both regarding the classification of the study (under investigation)
	Contact	
	Submission date	pending
	Approval	pending
5.	Associated Partner	PGNA [Clinical site in Greece, prospective Associated Partner]
	Committee	Ethics Committee, Research Council, University General Hospital of Alexandroupoli
	Contact	University Campus, Alexandroupoli, 68100 Greece griatryp3@pgna.gr
	Submission date	19.11.2025, protocol no. 61022/19-11-2025
	Approval	Approved on 11.12.2025, Protocol no. ΕΣ 32/29/11-12-2025,

3.4.2. Clinical Study B2

6.	Beneficiary	1 – ATHENA
	Committee	ATHENA Research Ethics Committee, Athens, Greece

Contact	griatryp3@pgna.gr
Submission date	15.04.2025, protocol no. 53-15/04/2025
Approval	Approved on 29.04.2025, Protocol no. 54-29/04/2025

3.4.3. Clinical Study B3

7.	Beneficiary	1 – ATHENA
	Committee	ATHENA Research Ethics Committee, Athens, Greece
	Contact	griatryp3@pgna.gr
	Submission date	pending
	Approval	pending

3.4.4. Clinical Study B4

8.	Beneficiary	9 – TAU
	Committee	FIMEA: The Finnish Medicines Agency P.O. Box 55, FI-00034 FIMEA, Finland
	Contact	registry@fimea.fi
	Submission date	15.10.2024
	Approval	Approved on 15.04.2025, Protocol no. FIMEA/2025/001098-5

3.4.5. Other

Although not explicitly mentioned in the DoA, the work during the 2nd year required the implementation of one additional study involving healthy volunteers and 2 surveys:

- An early feasibility study of the ThrombUS+ compression ultrasound module in healthy adult volunteers. The aim is to assess the ability of the module to compress tissue and acquire ultrasound videos.
- A **system usability study to assess the DICOM anonymization software** (US-DICOMizer) developed by ATHENA for use by ThrombUS+ team members to anonymize medical ultrasound data. This involves the administration of 2 related existing questionnaires, the SUS - system usability scale (J.R. Lewis, The System Usability Scale: Past, Present, and Future. Int J Hum-Comput Interact, 34 (2018), pp. 577-590, 10.1080/10447318.2018.1455307) and the PSSUQ - Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire (Lewis, J. R., 1990, Psychometric evaluation of a post-study system usability questionnaire: The PSSUQ (Tech. Report 54.535). Boca Raton, FL: International Business Machines Corp". Participants are clinical experts of the ThrombUS+ team who have used the anonymization software developed in the project.
- A **short public survey** that aims to probe public opinion on deep vein thrombosis. The goal is to inform the co-design approach of the project, enrich project communication activities, and implement public engagement. Participants are anonymous ThrombUS+ web site visitors.

Before the implementation of the feasibility study and the 2 surveys, ethics approvals were granted as follows:

3.4.5.1. Pilot experimental study of the ThrombUS+ compression ultrasound module

9.	Beneficiary	2 – KTU
	Committee	Kaunas Regional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee, Kaunas, Lithuania
	Contact	A. Mickevičiaus g. 9, LT 44307 Kaunas, Lithuania, kaunorbtek@ismuni.lt
	Submission date	24.04.2025
	Approval	Approved on 09.05.2025. Protocol no. BE-2-67/2025-05-09

3.4.5.2. System usability study to assess the DICOM anonymization software

10.	Beneficiary	1 – ATHENA
	Committee	ATHENA Research Ethics Committee, Athens, Greece
	Contact	griatryp3@pgna.gr
	Submission date	14.07.2025
	Approval	Approved on 31.07.2025, Protocol no. 59-31/07/2025

3.4.5.3. Short public survey

11.	Beneficiary	1 – ATHENA
	Committee	ATHENA Research Ethics Committee, Athens, Greece
	Contact	griatryp3@pgna.gr
	Submission date	14.07.2025
	Approval	Approved on 31.07.2025, Protocol no. 60-31/07/2025

3.5. Ethics requirements included in GA and how the Consortium addressed them

The Consortium complied to the ethics requirements included in the GA by providing the Independent Ethics Advisor full access to the files of the project, by seeking and receiving advice on how to best conduct their work with emphasis on the vulnerability of study participants, as well as adopting an ethics-by-design approach in their development of the final product before conducting any clinical studies on people.

In summary, regarding Studies B1, B3, and B4 a full risk assessment and mitigation and a full experimental safety assessment has been successfully conducted for the ThrombUS+ components and the outcomes were included in the protocol of the respective studies.

A discussion on study participants and their vulnerability is given for the Studies B planned for this 2nd project year:

- **Study B1** involves adult human participants undergoing routine ultrasound examinations, with an additional research scan performed using prototype components developed in the project in order to collect imaging data for research and algorithm development. Study participants will be recruited among those already participating in Study A. Since Study A does not include any burden additional to standard

care (conventional ultrasound scan as prescribed) the involvement of these patients to Study B1 (which involves an extra ultrasound scan with the components developed by the project) is deemed low risk and acceptable.

- **Study B2** involves recording physical activity of the lower limbs with wearable commercial sensors and cameras (strictly capturing only the lower limbs of the participants). The participants are healthy adult volunteers (self-reported healthy and self-reported non-pregnant). Since the physical activity involves basic physiotherapy exercises meant for standard patient post lower limb surgery care, the involvement of these participants is deemed low-risk, not particularly burdensome and acceptable.
- **Study B3** involves recording physical activity of the lower limbs with wearable activity sensors developed in the project and commercial cameras (strictly capturing only the lower limbs of the participants). As in Study B1, the participants are healthy adult volunteers (self-reported healthy and self-reported non-pregnant). Since the physical activity involves basic physiotherapy exercises meant for standard patient post lower limb surgery care, the involvement of these participants is deemed low-risk, not particularly burdensome and acceptable.
- **Study B4** involves the recording of electrical impedance plethysmography using the ThrombUS+ respective components. Participants are of two groups: patients with confirmed DVT in the lower limb and healthy volunteers. Since the participants include only adult, non-regnant individuals and with non-injured skin at the area of electrode application, their involvement is deemed low-risk, not particularly burdensome and acceptable.

4. Recommendations to the Consortium

The Consortium needs to speed up the ethics approval processes still pending for some of the sites scheduled to participate in Study A, however, the Consortium management is aware of the delays and taking all necessary steps to complete the processes.

Planning of Studies C needs to be completed in a timely manner and relevant ethics approvals have to be requested anew.

Development of study prototypes, as well as of the finished product need to take into account the need for minimizing data gathering, recruiting an adequate number of study participants. Informing participants adequately about the product's strengths and limitations. WP9 includes some steps to ensure that the finished product - should it prove clinically successful - is affordable, easy to use and safe for the prospective customers, however the Consortium management has been made aware that a bigger effort should be made in order for the finished product to be available to all those that would benefit from it, not only those that can afford it.

Discussion on Studies C will take place during the 3rd year of the project, and respective recommendations will be recorded in Deliverable D10.4 due Dec 2026.

5. Recommendations to the Commission/Executive Agency/Funding Body

None at this point, as no ethical or legal issues that cannot be resolved have been identified. The Consortium adheres to the provisions of relevant regulatory frameworks and the GA, they have asked for and received necessary guidance and they possess the tools and apply the indicated methodologies for completing their project successfully.